

ASSESSMENT OF TOTAL PRODUCTIVE MAINTENANCE IMPLEMENTATION: BASIS OF MAINTENANCE PERFORMANCE IMPROVEMENT IN PHARMA A MANUFACTURING PLANT

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ABSTRACT

The pharmaceutical industry, vital in producing life-saving drugs, confronts the challenge of maintaining high-quality standards while minimizing costs and downtime. Total Productive Maintenance (TPM) offers a comprehensive approach to optimize production equipment performance and reduce unplanned downtime, providing a solution to enhance productivity and ensure product quality and safety. This research aimed to comprehensively assess the existing maintenance program through the lens of eight Total Productive Maintenance (TPM) pillars, while concurrently gauging the level of awareness and readiness toward TPM implementation in the Pharma A Manufacturing plant. Additionally, the study aimed to identify disparities in TPM pillar implementation across the plant and explore variations in awareness and readiness levels. To achieve these objectives, primary data was collected from 25 department supervisors through a survey questionnaire, while secondary data was gathered from the perspective of the Operational Excellence (OE) Lead. The results showcased divergent levels of TPM pillar implementation and varying degrees of awareness and readiness among participants. Furthermore, specific action plans were formulated to bolster TPM implementation within the company. This research adds valuable insights to the existing knowledge on TPM implementation and offers practical recommendations tailored to the pharmaceutical industry's needs.

Keywords: *TPM, TPM Pillars, maintenance, pharmaceutical manufacturing, operational excellence*

INTRODUCTION

Nature and Scope of the Problem Investigated

The pharmaceutical industry is facing increasing pressure to maintain high-quality standards and productivity while minimizing costs and production downtime. A well-executed maintenance program is crucial for achieving these objectives. Total Productive Maintenance (TPM) is a holistic approach to maintenance that optimizes production equipment performance and reduces unplanned downtime. However, the unique characteristics of pharmaceutical production processes present challenges for implementing TPM, such as the need for cleanliness and sterility. Despite the potential benefits of TPM, its implementation in the pharmaceutical industry is relatively under-researched. This study aims to assess the current state of TPM implementation in Pharma A's manufacturing plant, identify areas for improvement, and propose action plans.

Research Objectives

1. Determine the existing maintenance program of the Pharma A manufacturing plant in terms of TPM 8 Pillars;
2. Identify Pharma A's level of awareness and readiness of pharma A manufacturing plant towards TPM in terms of TPM 8 Pillars;
3. Differentiate the level of awareness and readiness of pharma A manufacturing plant towards TPM; and
4. Suggest action plans needed to improve the TPM implementation in the pharma A manufacturing plant

Research Framework

The conceptual framework of this research was designed to identify the necessary action plan to improve the implementation of Total Productive Maintenance (TPM) in a pharmaceutical manufacturing plant. The framework was based on the Input-Process-Output process flow and takes into account the eight pillars of the TPM methodology. The data gathered for this study focused on the existing maintenance program, the level of awareness and readiness towards TPM within the company, and any differences observed. These pillars served as the foundation for developing an action plan to expedite the company's TPM implementation process. The study's findings can be utilized to create a roadmap for the successful implementation of TPM in the pharmaceutical manufacturing plant.

Figure 1: Research Conceptual Paradigm

Research Significance

The investigation of Total Productive Maintenance (TPM) implementation in Pharma A manufacturing plant contributed to the existing knowledge on TPM, particularly in the pharmaceutical industry. The findings provided insights into areas that needed improvement and proposed action plans to enhance the maintenance program. Practically, the study offered guidance for other manufacturing plants planning to implement TPM or improve their maintenance practices. Policy-wise, the study informed the development of guidelines or standards for TPM implementation, aligning with Good Manufacturing Practice (cGMP) standards. Lastly, from a social action perspective, the study's outcomes had a positive impact on employee safety, community well-being, and the production of high-quality medicines, while promoting environmental sustainability through reduced waste and energy consumption.

Scope and Limitation

This study evaluated the implementation of TPM in Pharma A manufacturing plant located in Biñan City, Laguna. It focused on assessing the implementation level of TPM in Pharma A based on the perspective of the OE lead using secondary data obtained from the company's records. The study involved 25 company supervisors of Pharma A manufacturing plant and aimed to investigate the existing maintenance program and the level of awareness, readiness, and differences towards TPM, focusing on its eight pillars. However, the study's findings are limited to the Pharma A manufacturing plant and cannot be extended to other pharmaceutical companies or other industries.

Definition of Terms

The following terms were defined operationally and conceptually to provide readers with a clear understanding of the study:

Autonomous Maintenance - It is a TPM pillar that refers to the practice of transferring routine maintenance tasks from the maintenance team to the production team.

Development Management - This TPM pillar focuses on developing a plan to improve the overall maintenance process continually.

Education and Training - This TPM pillar involves training employees on equipment maintenance and repair procedures, as well as developing their problem-solving and troubleshooting skills.

Focused Maintenance - This is another TPM pillar that involves identifying and addressing the root causes of equipment failures.

Office TPM - It is a TPM pillar that refers to the application of TPM principles to office and administrative processes. It aims to reduce waste, improve efficiency, and streamline office operations.

Operational Excellence (OE) - wastewater coming out from manufacturing companies

Planned Maintenance - It is a TPM pillar that refers to the practice of scheduling maintenance activities based on predetermined maintenance intervals. It aims to reduce unplanned downtime and equipment failures.

Quality Maintenance - This TPM pillar focuses on maintaining the equipment and processes to ensure product quality.

Safety, Health, and Environment - In this TPM pillar, the focus is on ensuring that maintenance activities are conducted in a safe and environmentally friendly manner.

Review of Pertinent Literatures

Total Productive Maintenance (TPM) is a methodology used in manufacturing plants to maximize equipment effectiveness and efficiency while minimizing downtime (Nakajima, 1988). TPM involves the entire workforce in equipment maintenance, aiming to achieve zero breakdowns, zero defects, and zero accidents (Bamber et al., 1999). The eight pillars of TPM, as proposed by Nakajima, include autonomous maintenance, focused maintenance, planned maintenance, quality management, education and training, safety, health, and environment, office TPM, and development management (Trout, 2023).

TPM was developed in Japan during the late 1950s and early 1960s by Seiichi Nakajima as a response to the country's growing industrial sector (Nakajima, 1988). TPM's focus on improving equipment reliability, reducing downtime, and increasing the life of equipment has made it popular in various industries worldwide (Dogra et al., 2011). The integration of TPM principles in areas beyond machine maintenance, such as safety, health, and the environment, further enhances its effectiveness (Ramachandra & Pai, 2016). Successful TPM implementation involves overcoming challenges like a lack of quick implementation methods, inadequate resources, and resistance to change. To

achieve successful TPM, financial and managerial support, employee education and training, effective organizational phases, motivating incentives, teamwork, and a culture shift are critical factors (Sahib, 2016).

Studies have shown that TPM implementation leads to improvements in Overall Equipment Effectiveness (OEE) in various industries. TPM has been successfully applied in industries such as the milk industry (Bajwa, 2018), the sewing process in the footwear industry (Mridha et al., 2020), the vehicle industry (Abdul & Ping, 2019), the casting business (Anandane, 2018), the machine shop (Pandey et al., 2019), the aircraft industry (Feliciano, 2015), and other industries have all participated in TPM application research. In the Philippines, TPM implementation has been studied in various industries such as cement paper bag manufacturing (Halili & Norona, 2021) and rice-producing sectors demonstrating the benefits of TPM in terms of equipment utilization and yield improvement (Saflor, 2021).

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a quantitative-descriptive research design to determine the existing maintenance program at Pharma A's manufacturing plant, assess the level of awareness and readiness towards Total Productive Maintenance (TPM), and identify the differences in the level of awareness and readiness that were used to develop action plans to improve TPM implementation. This study represents the company's existing maintenance program based on secondary data and the level of awareness and readiness towards TPM and its differences as measured by primary data.

Research Locale

The research was conducted in Pharma A manufacturing plant located in Laguna. Its representatives answered the survey form related to the study. Research questions were answered by the Pharma A manufacturing plant department supervisors since they are the ones who are assigned to implement the TPM in their respective departments. Thus, it is their perception of TPM implementation that is considered essential for this study.

Population and Sampling Design

The population for the study consisted of department supervisors who were working at Pharma A's manufacturing plant in Laguna, Philippines, and were responsible for implementing Total Productive Maintenance (TPM) in their respective departments. The sampling design employed for this research was total enumeration, which included all twenty-five department supervisors at the manufacturing facility. This approach ensured that every member of the target population was included in the study, providing a representative sample and eliminating the need for statistical inferences. By surveying all department supervisors, the study aimed to gain comprehensive insights into the level of awareness and readiness toward TPM implementation. Subsequently, based on the

findings, effective action plans were developed to improve TPM implementation at the plant.

Research Instrument

The research instrument used for data collection in this study was a semi-structured survey questionnaire. This instrument was developed based on relevant literature concerning the activities of the Total Productive Maintenance (TPM) pillars. The questionnaire consisted of two parts: Part I gathered demographic information from the respondents, and Part II assessed the level of awareness and readiness of Pharma A's manufacturing plant towards TPM implementation. Part II included questions related to each TPM pillar, using a Likert scale to measure respondents' agreement or disagreement with the statements. To ensure the validity and reliability of the questionnaire, a pilot test was conducted with two department managers who were not part of the final list of participants. Minor changes were made based on their feedback, rendering the instrument valid and reliable for data collection.

Data Gathering Procedure

The data gathering procedure employed a survey questionnaire distributed to the twenty-five department supervisors at Pharma A's manufacturing facility in Laguna, Philippines. The questionnaire consisted of closed-ended queries with Likert scale response options to assess the supervisors' level of awareness and readiness toward Total Productive Maintenance (TPM) implementation. Additionally, the study collected secondary data from the OE Lead of the company, who played a crucial role in overseeing Operational Excellence at the plant. The OE Lead provided relevant information on the existing maintenance program and the level of TPM implementation, acquired through documentation review and assessments.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Existing maintenance program of Pharma A manufacturing plant

The company's OE Lead assessment of the existing maintenance program of the Pharma A Manufacturing Plant showed that the implementation of TPM pillars varied across the plant. The results show that the plant has implemented Autonomous Maintenance, with a percentage of 40%. The pilot equipment has been selected, and the initial cleaning has been done. However, more work is needed to fully implement Autonomous Maintenance across all equipment. The implementation of Planned Maintenance has a percentage of 30%, and the company has predictive maintenance tools such as thermal scanners and vibration analyzers. There is a need for the recalibration of MTTR and MTBF metrics. The Education and Training pillar has a percentage of 30% with a TPM Steering Committee, TPM Implementation Roadmap, and TPM Walks in place. The Safety, Health, and Environment pillar has a percentage of 50%, with the plan having an established ESH Team and specific programs and initiatives already implemented. Meanwhile, efforts to

support the Focused Maintenance, Quality Maintenance, Office TPM, and Development Management pillars have not been implemented yet.

Identified Pharma A's level of awareness and readiness of pharma A manufacturing plant towards TPM in terms of its pillars

The study found that while the respondents generally have a consistently high awareness of the importance of all eight TPM pillars, the company's level of readiness for TPM implementation varies. The results show a gap and suggest that the company needs to improve its readiness for autonomous maintenance, focused maintenance, planned maintenance, quality maintenance, education and training, Safety, Health, and Environment, and development management pillars. The study highlighted the importance of prioritizing employee training and development, allocating sufficient resources, and implementing effective maintenance systems and procedures to achieve successful TPM implementation. Enhancing readiness for TPM implementation can lead to improved equipment performance, reduced maintenance costs, increased productivity, and customer satisfaction, all of which are critical for maintaining competitiveness in the business environment.

Difference between the level of awareness and readiness of pharma A manufacturing plant towards TPM in terms of its pillars

The study evaluates the level of awareness and readiness of a Pharma A manufacturing plant towards TPM in terms of its pillars. The results indicate that there is a higher level of awareness compared to the level of readiness for all pillars, except for safety, health, and environment which posted a high level of awareness and readiness. The study suggests that there is a need for further action to fully implement all other pillars of TPM, as the level of readiness is at a moderate level, while simultaneously maintaining existing SHE practices. This indicates a lot of room for improvement in consistently applying TPM practices.

Action plans needed to improve the TPM implementation in the pharma A manufacturing plant:

The study provides actionable recommendations to enhance Total Productive Maintenance (TPM) implementation at Pharma A manufacturing plant. To improve employee performance and effectiveness, the company should offer necessary resources and support, including equipment manuals, basic tools, and workshops for risk assessment and root cause analysis. Implementing efficient Preventive Maintenance (PM) and Predictive Maintenance (PdM) systems through regular inspections, cleaning, lubrication, component replacement, and root cause analysis can address underlying issues that lead to failures. Quality control can be enhanced by conducting regular equipment inspections, employing a computerized maintenance management system, and establishing a cross-functional team to address equipment problems. Developing a skilled and motivated workforce can be achieved through training programs, cross-functional collaboration, and incentivizing employee engagement and participation.

Additionally, optimizing the company can be achieved by improving standard operating procedures, streamlining processes, conducting cost analysis, and implementing the 5S methodology.

Conclusions

The study concludes that while the Pharma A manufacturing plant has made progress in implementing TPM pillars, there are areas that require improvement. For optimal benefits, a comprehensive approach that encompasses all TPM pillars is necessary, involving commitment from top management, plant managers, and operators. The research identified high levels of awareness towards TPM across all pillars, but readiness for implementation varied, with most pillars scoring moderately in readiness. This indicates a need for improvement in readiness for TPM implementation. Notably, the level of awareness was higher than the level of readiness, suggesting that further action is required to fully implement TPM practices. To enhance TPM implementation, the company should focus on improving readiness and take necessary actions for the consistent application of TPM practices throughout the organization.

Recommendations

The study offers several recommendations to address its limitations and enhance future research. Firstly, to gain a broader perspective, involving a larger sample of customer participation could provide valuable insights. Secondly, a Mixed Method approach with in-depth interviews may uncover a deeper understanding of the realm of TPM implementation. Additionally, expanding the assessment process by involving other stakeholders beyond the Operational Excellence (OE) Lead could yield a more comprehensive evaluation. Moreover, exploring successful TPM implementation in allied pharmaceutical industries and identifying best practices is encouraged. Investigating the effectiveness of communication strategies in promoting TPM awareness among employees is also a potential area for future exploration. Further studies in pharmaceutical manufacturing and other industries can assess TPM implementation effectiveness. Understanding the role of leadership and technology in facilitating TPM implementation and employee readiness holds promise for future research. Developing a standardized approach to TPM implementation and considering longitudinal studies to evaluate its long-term impact is also worth exploring, despite the time investment involved. These recommendations aim to contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of TPM implementation and its implications for organizations and industries.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher complied with the basic standards of research ethics and also followed the Data Privacy Act in the collection and process of data gathered.

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